

STRUNE – AN INTERACTIVE AUDIO-VISUAL INSTALLATION INSPIRED BY STRING THEORY

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ABSTRACT

“Strune” is an interactive audio-visual installation inspired by the string theory of particle physics, presented in January 2018 in Galerija SC in Zagreb, Croatia. “Strune” consists of a 15-meter-long tensioned piano wire, supported by a resonant plywood box, and is driven to resonate by an all-thread bolt attached to a subwoofer. A Max/Msp patch is used to process the vibrations propagating on the string according to a dataset simulating 13TeV LHC particle collisions. Correspondingly, the process brings out a series of frequencies akin to the families of particles produced by the resonances of quantum mechanical strings. Design details and audience experiences are described. Video of the opening present at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JUSO-6ykulo>

1. INTRODUCTION

“Strune” was commissioned in late 2016 by “Kultura Promjene” as an open-ended artistic residency. The hope from both commissioner and commissioned artists Hrvoje Hiršl (in later text HH) and Davor Branimir Vincze (in later text DBV), was to create compelling interdisciplinary project, which would go beyond the boundaries of each of their respective art practices. Since both HH and DBV share the fascination for science and the potential of its implementation in arts, it was very early on decided to create an audio-visual installation that would transpire relations between music and physics in a broader sense.

The first step we (HH&DBV) took was to revisit the teachings of Pythagoras who is “thought to be the first to conduct scientific investigations on the nature of sound. Using the monochord, he [Pythagoras] discovered the harmonic relationships between vibrating strings of different lengths (...). He noticed that two stretched strings, whose lengths are in the ratio 2:1, produced the same note an octave apart” [1]. It was interesting to discover that Pythagoras went even further, relating musical harmony to the order in the structure of the cosmos. Echoes of this musical model of the cosmos can also be traced in the currently popular string theory of particle physics.

String theory provides a theoretical framework to link four fundamental forces of nature: electromagnetism, weak force, strong force and gravity. The problem arises

in attempting to combine quantum mechanics with Einstein’s theory of relativity. String theory offers an explanation that reconciles the two by theorizing that the entire universe is made of incredibly small one-dimensional strings (size about 10^{-33} cm). By doing so, the strings vibrate in a space with more than the familiar three spatial dimensions, and produce particles as resonances of the string. [2]

Having realized these connections, we decided to use the existing analogies between Pythagoras’s, musical string and string theory in the conception of our audio-visual installation. Thinking about how we could present the hidden dimensions, we noted that Fletcher [3], describes similarities between string theory and coiled springs. As stated in [3] “many of the possible physical dimensions of the string [according to the string theory] are hidden because they are coiled up into some sort of small structure concealed within the string”. The author then continues explaining that a special type of spring which he calls hyperhelix “is a helical structure where the coils of the helix are found to also consist of a helix with a much smaller helical diameter though a similar helical pitch angle (see Figure 1)” [3]. The author’s idea behind the article was that “the hyperhelix might be a fruitful analogy by which physicists can convey to non-experts a picture of part of the nature of string theory” [3]. We were immediately tempted to portraying this idea.

Figure 1. Modified from Fletcher [3] (a) Ideal string, 0 hidden dimensions, (b) Helix, 1 hidden dimension, (c) hyperhelix, 2 hidden dimensions.

Figure 2. (a) Ideal string - 0 hidden dimensions, (b) Piano string – its thickness acts as a hidden dimension.

At first we explored several concepts that could make an analogy between hidden dimensions and our installation (as described in the section “Hardware design”). In the end, we concluded that it would be best to start with what Fletcher calls hyperhelix of order zero – a simple string – and use this installation as a precursor for further sound research. We noted that a simple, physical string has a “hidden dimensions” due to its thickness, as illustrated in Figure 2. Exploiting this fact, we decided to expose the inharmonic frequencies of a tensioned string and present them as hidden dimensions.

Finally, knowing that this would not be the first work employing wires, strings or springs, we wanted to make sure that we were not mining in a field that was already fully excavated. Some of more interesting installations we found were “Music on a long thin wire” (1977) by Alvin Lucier, “Tripwire” (2011) by Ashley Fure and “One or more schachtophones” (2016) by Damir Indoš. Nevertheless, none of the works we examined had emphasis on relation between strings and particle physics as their guiding principle. This made us confident that by making this audio-visual installation, we were to end up with sonic results that were captivating and unique.

2. CREATIVE APPROACH

Working on Strune involved three phases: conception, exploration and realization. The conception phase started before the commissioner confirmed the exact exhibition space, but it was speculated that it would be a much smaller gallery than it finally was. As such, we conceived of the room as the nucleus of an atom with multiple strings spanned across the space representing subatomic particles. Even though this initial concept was not realized, many of our initial goals remained unchanged. Our idea was to make the installation look simple from the outside, but have complex inner mechanism. It had to be immersive, lure visitors’ curiosity, but never fully reveal itself. Connections between string theory and string mechanics were to be hinted at, but not scholastically explained. We decided to allow a limited interaction, sufficient to keep the audience engaged, but without the result being dependent on its presence.

The exploration phase consisted of series of smaller size simulations to test diverse parts of the future installation. We examined different types of springs and string, and were thus able to decide upon the appropriate dimensions and thickness. There was also an issue of how to get the wire to vibrate. Diverse mechanisms were discussed, some of which involved having hanging metal rods that the audience could interact with, electrical motor vibra-

tors, solenoid electromotors, sine wave generators, loudspeakers or electromagnetic actuators. The resonant box came into play as we accidentally tied one of the wires against a large cupboard and noticed that it passively amplified the sound. Later we constructed a miniature resonant box to test the amount of amplification we could expect. As we intended to add transducers and put them onto the resonant box, we had to try out how they sound with materials ranging from metal to plastic, before eventually settling for simple plywood. Overall this phase helped to narrow down the types of tools we used.

Figure 3. A ground plan of Galerija SC, the exhibition space (nr.7), precisely 15,73m long and 8,02m wide. [4]

During the realization phase, in which we turned these test runs into a fully-fledged installation, numerous limitations and constraints emerged that had to be creatively surmounted. The size of the gallery space was just one of them. The sound of a single string in such a large room (15m x 8m x 5m) might have been easily absorbed, especially if the room was full of people. See the ground plan in Figure 3. Furthermore, we were concerned that our resonator would not enhance the frequencies of our string sufficiently. Luckily that was not the case. An even greater issue was that the soft brick wall did not hold bolts and hooks properly. It was a struggle to find the right position and angle, to hold the resonator and the tensor ratchet mechanism in place once the string was maximally tensioned.

The biggest problem, however, was to find the most effective way to induce vibration. Providing visitors with a metal baton and instructing them to hit the string would have been a nice way to engage the audience, but it would risk generating a completely unpredictable sounding result. The string might have been activated by a sine wave generator or a transducer, but the device itself would always be louder than the vibrating string. Solenoid electromotor sounded great, yet no matter how well we fixed them, they would eventually manage to drift slightly to the side, at which point they would miss the string entirely. We considered and rejected electromagnetic actuators because on such a long string they were not generating sufficient amplitude and to obtain rich harmonic spectrum would require having either a movable or multiple fixed actuators, none of which we wanted.

Figure 4. A subwoofer with an all-thread bolt attached.

Eventually, having noticed that a subwoofer membrane produces large amplitude movements whenever it plays extremely low frequencies, we added a threaded bolt to subwoofer’s center and created a friction similar to a bow. This method finally gave the result we were so eagerly looking for (see Figure 4).

3. HARDWARE DESIGN

3.1 Design Exploration and Experimentation

Figure 5. A model of the initial concept. The strings have been artificially emphasized in Adobe Illustrator.

The first idea corresponded to the model in Figure 5. It was a rather ambitious plan that involved spanning more than fifty strings across the entire exhibition space, each with its unique length and angle, so to create an immersive maze through which the audience could navigate freely. Even though this would barely be achievable with the awarded funding, the main constraint was the gallery manager’s unwillingness to allow us to drill numerous holes in the wall necessary to attach all these strings. Another issue with this idea was creating the simplest possi-

ble mechanism that could make strings vibrate: One small electrical vibrator for each string could have worked, but this would require complex wiring, which would disrupt the elegance of simply having strings spanned across the room. Since, according to this idea, each string should have had a precisely defined frequency, we quickly ran into another problem. The base frequency of very long strings is below human hearing threshold. As we tested spanning strings in various length, we realized that activating a tensioned string longer than about 2 meters would just result in a buzzing metal noise and overtones of that string, but one could not hear the fundamental frequency. In order to solve this problem, one would have to create series of supporting structures, which would bend these long diagonal wires on several nodes, and thus create a series of pitches along one string. This of course would have been a constructional nightmare.

Furthermore, there was an issue of having to retune each string numerous times, since most probably the initial tension would not have held for more than a day. These constrains made us rework the concept into something more stable and elegant.

Figure 6. Example spring sound propagation modes. (a) longitudinal, (b) transverse and (c) torsional.

Our next idea was to come closer to Fletcher’s order 1 helix and use one long metal spring that we would span across the entire space. The spring would thus symbolize an enlarged version of a subatomic particle existing in multiple dimensions. In addition, springs have several different modes of propagating sound from one side to the other (see Figure 6), and the interaction between these modes results in cutoff frequency around 4 – 6kHz, contributing to the spring’s equalization and giving the spring its characteristic sound [5]. The installation was supposed to function in a manner similar to the Space Phone toy (see Figure 7), only much bigger in size and interactive, so that the audience could in pairs speak on one and listen on the other side of the gallery space. We were lucky to find an experienced artisan in Zagreb that could make custom springs with the diameter of the loop being as small as 5mm. The downside was that the maximum length that he was able to produce was 3 meters, so in order to cover the exhibition space that was 15 meters long, we would have had to solder five of these springs

into one, and there was a risk that these five parts could break during the manipulation with the string. As we tried spanning the spring, we realized that spring of such length bends downwards, so one would need to put at least 5 nylon threads from the ceiling to hold the spring straight across its path. This solution had several disadvantages. It would be visually displeasing, it would interfere with the wave propagation along the spring, it would be nearly impossible to hang it from the ceiling of the given exhibition space, and in the end it would still not be completely straight.

Figure 7. An example of Space Phone Toy. [6]

The next modification of this idea that we tried out was inserting a single piano wire through the middle of the spring, as if the spring were the sock covering the entire length of the string. We thought that the activation mechanism might make string vibrate, which in turn would hit against the spring, and produce additional interesting vibrations on the spring as well. As soon as we tried this experiment, we came to the conclusion that our design was utopic. No matter what type of force we applied to make the string vibrate, the vibration would quickly get damped due to a rather heavy spring. The spring would shake once and then kept hanging on the string thus extinguishing any further wave propagation. However, these trials were not in vain as they brought us closer to the final design.

3.2 Final Implementation

In our final design, we decided to go for an absolutely simple single piano wire across the entire space. There were 6 different wire thicknesses (0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.35 and 1.7 millimeters) that we acquired and tested. The thinnest two were too brittle and would break when spanned with such a high tension. The thickest two were pulling the construction mechanism that was holding them from the wall even before they could be tightened to create any sound. The middle two gave optimal results, yet we decided to go for the 1.0mm string, as it was slightly louder and more resonant than the 0.75mm one. The string was attached to the wall via simple ratchet mechanism (see Figure 8).

Despite the good performance of one millimeter string, our concern was that the sound of a single string in such a big space might get lost, which is why we decided to add

a resonant box and attach the string to its front side (see Figure 9). A simple plywood was used for the construction, creating a box having the following dimensions: 150cm x 100cm x 99cm. It was constructed in such a way that it can be hung with its back against the wall and with a small 30 cm opening on the lower front side that could emit the sound. The construction details of the resonant box can be seen in Figure 10.

Figure 8. Ratchet mechanism was holding the string to the wall on the opposite side from the resonant box.

Figure 9. A plywood resonant box. String enhanced in blue. Transducers encircled in red.

Based on our previous experimentation, we knew that the string of such length would not produce an audible low-frequency pitch, but rather a cluster containing over-tones of the fundamental pitch and the noise of wire rubbing against its activation mechanism. At first it seemed that this might not give a desirable effect, but as soon as we decided to expand the sound via feedback loop and electronics, we were actually happy that the sonic result was richer than a single pitched sound. Four VX-GH92 transducers have been used. Each was fixed to one of the four lateral sides. These were also the only available sides, since the front side had the string attached to it and the back side had hooks holding it to the wall. The transducers were positioned in the corners, off-center on the

spots that had maximum resonance (see Figure 8). The signal from the computer was amplified before reaching the transducers via Dayton Audio DTA-1 Class T mini amplifiers.

Figure 10. Design of the resonant box.

To make the string vibrate, we were sending inaudible frequencies (15-25 Hz) to a subwoofer that had an all-thread bolt glued to its center. It was positioned on a stand so that the middle part of the bolt was touching the string. In this way, as subwoofer would quickly move up and down, allowing the threads of the bolt to scratch the string, producing a loud and noisy sound. (see Figure 4).

Finally, we needed to record the string, so that its sound could be fed back to transducers. Three types of microphone have been used for this purpose: cardioid Behringer C/2 condenser microphone (1), simple guitar pick-up (2) and Korg CM-200 contact microphone (3). The cardioid was positioned at the mechanism holding the wire to the wall and could capture inharmonic partials at the string’s origin along with some ambient room sound made by the audience. The guitar pick-up was put in the middle and recorded a pure sound of the string that resulted from disruption of pick-up’s magnetic field. The contact microphone was placed on the bottom side of the resonant box and could thus capture the response of the resonant box.

4. INTERACTION DESIGN

The interaction, sound processing and automation were all designed as Max/Msp patch¹ (see Figure 11). The patch consisted of 5 processing modules, each treating the input signal in a special way. These treatments were governed by simulated LHC particle collision datasets produced by Brian Shuve using the MadGraph software (see figure 12). As was explained by Brian Shuve, “MadGraph allows us to simulate what happens in high-energy particle collisions. It simulates the initial proton collision at the LHC, the production of a particle moving in the extra dimension, and then its decay back into normal particles that are not moving in the extra dimension.”

¹ The Max/Msp patch can be downloaded here for free: <https://stanford.box.com/s/og79mhfzuvurldskjulbpqhkwsqyuero>

The generated data represent production of a new particle called a Kalauze-Klein (KK) graviton. A total of 50,000 13TeV LHC collisions were simulated using MadGraph software. The recorded data represents the perpendicular direction momenta and energies of each muon-antimuon pair produced by the decay of the simulated KK graviton. This data was normalised and subsequently divided into five groups, each group directly controlling the parameters of its respective processing module. In Max/Msp these control values define time intervals in which things get triggered, ranges of transposition, time delay, filter amount, grain size and all other sound manipulation parameters.

Figure 11. An interface of Max/Msp patch by DBV.

The patch was running on a Macbook Pro with OS 10.12.4, it was connected to a Focusrite Scarlett 18i20 audio interface, which was receiving 3 inputs (the previously mentioned three microphones) and was connected to 9 outputs. At first we intended to have 5 outputs: 1 for the string activator (subwoofer) and 4 for the transducers. However, due to the small size of transducers that could only output frequencies above 120Hz, we realized the need for proper speakers that can also play the lower part of the spectrum, which led to implementing additional Solton aart 12A loudspeakers in four corners of the room.

Module 1 (M1) receives the signal from the condenser microphone, but only the velocity of the signal is used to control the amplitude of the computer-generated white noise. In this way the noise from the gallery space could influence the sound result without the risk of overly feeding back. The noise gets filtered with a bandpass filter that has a high gain, narrow Q and center frequency. Each channel has a different center frequency, which is continuously changing.

Module 2 (M2) can randomly turn pick-up microphone on and off and record a sound file lasting 3-5 seconds. This sound file will first get filtered and shifted lower, then looped so that each iteration has a short delay and microtonal transposition up, while its gain gets reduced, so that the sound fades out after 10-15 iterations. It sounds as if something is rising and disappearing at the same time.

```

#*****
# Running parameters
#*****
#
#*****
# Tag name for the run (one word)
#*****
tag_1 = run_tag ! name of the run
#*****
# Number of events and rnd seed
# Warning: Do not generate more than 1M events in a single run
# If you want to run Pythia, avoid more than 50k events in a run.
#*****
50000 = nevents ! Number of unweighted events requested
21 = iseed ! rnd seed (0=assigned automatically=default)
#*****
# Collider type and energy
# lpp: 0=No PDF, 1=proton, -1=antiproton, 2=photon from proton,
# *****
1 = lpp1 ! beam 1 type
1 = lpp2 ! beam 2 type
6500.0 = ebeam1 ! beam 1 total energy in GeV
6500.0 = ebeam2 ! beam 2 total energy in GeV
#*****
# Beam polarization from -100 (left-handed) to 100 (right-handed)
#*****
0.0 = polbeam1 ! beam polarization for beam 1
0.0 = polbeam2 ! beam polarization for beam 2
#*****

```

Figure 12. An example of the code in MadGraph by Brian Shuve.²

Module 3 (M3) receives its input from the contact microphone, but each of the 4 channels is passing the signal for a brief moment (0.3 – 3 seconds) every few seconds. This signal is then delayed and manipulated to create a short glissando. Even though transducers and loudspeakers receive the same signal, in this module, there is an additional time offset between the two. This process relies on the fact that the string resonance is fed back into the system, but since the signal is processed discontinuously (in short time intervals) there is no risk of having an explosive build up of acoustic feedback.

Module 4 (M4) creates granular synthesis sounds. Instead of a microphone, it uses a 10-second-long recording of the string being activated by a short impulse and left to spontaneously decay. The sound file was recorded in the same gallery space. The principle of the granular synthesis [7] is that it takes sound snippets of various lengths from a random position in the buffer (in this case it was the previously recorded string). It repeats the process in variable rate, assigning these snippets (called grains) to multiple voices, thus creating an alternating granular sound that resembles the original sound file, but tends to be more vivid and textural. It is also possible to change the loudness and the speed of its playback (which automatically transposes pitch downwards when played slower or vice versa). For the purposes of this installation, 8 voices were created (each for one of the 4 transducers and 4 loudspeakers), but the voices can also get randomly muted and unmuted, conveying the feeling of sounds moving around the gallery.

² “For the actual data I created, I defined a 3-dimensional coordinate system where z is the coordinate along the direction of the incident beams, which collide. Conservation of momentum says that the total momentum in the x-y directions has to be zero after the collision, but because we have both an electron and a positron in the final state, this just says they have to be moving in opposite directions in the x-y directions. I pick out the part of its momentum that points in the x-direction of the electron and record it. Then I divide each momentum by the maximum momentum for the entire sample, so that each data point lies within the range 0-1.”

Module 5 (M5) receives its input via contact microphone. The input signal is fed back with a delay and a microtonal transposition, causing continuous build up of the feedback. Yet, this feedback signal being iteratively multiplied by a sine wave, results in a continuous glissando, which in turn prevents accumulation of identical frequencies that could result in ear piercing acoustical feedback. It thus produces a constant loudness swelling that diminishes as it reaches the upper velocity threshold that could be harmful for the listener or cause damage to the loudspeakers. The avoidance of unpleasant feedback is further reinforced by variation of the sine wave frequency, delay time, transposition and offset between transducers and loudspeakers. A simplified scheme of the entire algorithm can be seen in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Scheme of the algorithmic process that runs the installation.

Our interaction design had two slightly different versions. The first one was intended for the opening concert performance, and it was more loosely defined, so that we could trigger the subwoofer, control the velocity of input and output signal as well as some parameters such as transposition, onset, pitch shift and other. All of this has been done on Korg Nanokontrol2 and Akai MPD218 midi controller. Furthermore, we created a narrative gra-

ation by going from a relatively soft and atmospheric sound of module 1 all the way to a completely chaotic and loud module 5. Each module got presented only once (see Figure 14).

Figure 14. DBV and HH performing live in Zagreb on January 8th 2018.

The installation version, which ran during the subsequent week, was fully automated by the dataset. One list of values was used as a ‘clock’ that randomly switched between five modules, but the time it remained in the same module was diminishing from approximately one minute to several seconds. Each ‘tick’ of the ‘clock’ refreshed all of the above-stated parameters (filter gain, q and frequency in M1, delay and transposition amount in M2, time intervals in M3, granular synthesis values in M4, size, position, rate, speed, loudness in M5, etc.) by reading the next line of values from the dataset. In about an hour a full loop would be covered going from a calm situation to hectic jumping between the modules and would then restart. In this version, unlike during the concert, the audience was allowed to touch, pluck or hit the string or to interact via condenser microphone.

5. AUDIENCE EXPERIENCE AND RESPONSE

There were three aspects that we considered the most while reflecting upon the experience that audience will have while interacting with our piece: visual, aural and conceptual.

The visual aspect was intended to be the most direct and straightforward, making the mechanism as simple as possible and using several lights to accentuate only the most prominent elements of the installation. As can be seen on Figure 15, there were only three spot-lights used. One pointed out the connection of the string to the resonant box, while the other two illuminated the string itself. An additional spotlight pointed at the mixing table, but was only used during the opening concert. The audience mostly described the visuals as impressive, monolithic and elegant. Some visitors said that since the wire was so thin, they could not really see the entire string and it seemed as if the wire was mystically hovering one meter above the ground, which only further strengthened their

opinion of the visual aspects being very majestic. Most of the audience had no problem realizing that the string was the main source of sound, that the screw was driving the string, and that the plywood box served as a sort of resonator. Some of them however, raised a question about the mechanism behind the string activation or asked what exactly made the box resonate.

Figure 15. Galerija SC shortly before the opening concert.

While elaborating the acoustic aspects, we primarily aimed at making the installation immersive. Thus it was a pleasure to hear the majority of people comment that it seemed as if the string projected an aura onto the entire gallery space and to see the audience walk straight to the core of the installation – the resonant box. Another goal was to stress the contrast between the simple pre-processed sound (the string itself) and the rich post-processed sound (the electronics). To achieve that, the previously mentioned five modules were designed to be as diverse as possible. Some of them (like M1) kept the relation between the pre- and post-processed sound simple for the purposes of revealing the underlying principle. Here, each isolated string vibration was immediately followed by a slightly modified electronic sound. The other modules displayed a higher degree of complexity, deliberately concealing that connection. The audience response confirmed this hypothesis, since most of the visitors tapped, knocked, touched and yelled at various installation elements in order to find the underlying causality. A lot of them showed considerable surprise as they found out that the source of all sounds was a single vibrating wire. Finally, we wanted to make the experience of the opening concert to be special, which is why we allowed ourselves to break some rules during our 30 minutes long performance. Unlike the fully automated installation, during the performance many dataset-controlled parameters were triggered by HH and DBV. We also made the sounds significantly louder, displayed each module only once and ordered them in a way to form an ever-growing tension. The public mostly responded positively to our performance, saying that they enjoyed the dramatic development going from simple to more complex sound manipulations.

Conceptually, there was a desire to imply some commonalities between the principles of particle physics and principles of sound perception. Physicists manipulate

subatomic particles in order to create new types of particles or change and measure their properties. We did something similar by manipulating the vibration of the string in order to producing a whole range of new sounds. Particle physics also tries to indirectly prove existing phenomena, which our senses cannot perceive. Correspondingly, we exploited the fact that the rich timbre of our string contains a number of harmonic and inharmonic frequencies that our brain interprets as unified texture and exposed these “hidden” frequencies. Our goal was not to make this installation overly didactic, rather to awaken audience’s interest and raise some questions, without fully disclosing how the installation was made. In this sense we were very lucky to have more than hundred visitors during the opening night, most of them staying long after the opening performance, asking for explanation and playing around with the installation. The Mad-Graph-generated dataset was giving us seemingly statistical quantities, and one might argue that a random number generator could have been equally effective. Nevertheless, we wanted to reinforce the fact that sometimes there is an underlying correlation that might not be immediately apparent. Even those visitors that stuck around to ask questions uttered their contempt that they could not fully understand the mechanisms, or else it would have scraped the mystique of the piece they enjoyed so much. Short video of the opening night is available at [8].

6. SUMMARY AND FUTURE WORKS

“Strune” proved to be a successful implementation of some basic concepts of string theory into an artistic medium. It fulfilled most of its primary goals of being visually clear and simple, musically rich and complex, while allowing audience to explore. It created an imaginary, immersive space, which revealed some and concealed other aspects of its design. Just like a looped particle string, the installation was primarily based on the same sound being continuously fed back. Thanks to the dataset, it was functioning autonomously like a self-regulated system.

Figure 16 shows one of many possible alternatives to this project. Instead of strings, it would use springs, which in a way correspond better to Fletcher’s idea of hyperhelix as a symbol for multi-dimensional string. It would also bring us closer to the initial concept, in which the entire gallery space acted as one time-space continuum. Further advantages are that springs would not bend as they did when positioned horizontally, nor would they need to be tensioned like strings do. Moreover, springs have much richer timbre than strings and by having springs in various sizes, one could reduce the amount of electronic treatments that in the current version at times seem artificially imposed. Nevertheless, having completed and publicly presented this intriguing and fully functional version of installation, a foundation has been created upon which we can build our future sonic research.

Figure 16. A sketch of potential alternative for this installation.

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